

Geographical Access to Healthcare Services in Nigeria – A Review

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Abstract

The Nigerian economy is dwindling, the health system is failing, and the wellbeing of the citizenry is declining. The cost of living is high, the road network is poor, and many people lack enough to afford expensive healthcare, apart from paying an extra for transport to a long-distance health facility. The situation increases the tendency to delay or miss effective health care on a daily basis all over the country; especially in rural areas where infrastructural development is low. As effective treatment is delayed for a prolonged period, the severity of outcomes, hospitalisation and mortality are likely to occur. Are these the reasons for high maternal mortality, child mortality, HIV/AIDS, Tuberculosis, and low life expectancy in Nigeria? Health planners, over the years, have been focussing on financing healthcare with less consideration of the viability of facilities' locations. Thus, laudable projects over the years have become redundant or shut down shortly after commissioning. It is glaring that finance alone will not redeem the failing Nigerian health system. Therefore, healthcare planners and researchers must prioritise other dimensions of healthcare access such as geographical accessibility which they have ignored over the years.

Keywords: Geographical access, healthcare, health system, Nigeria.

Introduction

Access significantly impacts the utilisation of all forms of healthcare services and differential health outcomes of users (Makita-Ikouaya *et al.*, 2010; Simões and Almeida, 2011). Where studies on this subject are lacking, the planning and evaluation of the health systems may be difficult. Since planners are faced constantly with questions of suitability and equitability of interventions despite the limited disposable resources, the study of access becomes more paramount in the resource-poor countries. Less consideration of health care location accessibility in developing countries has contributed to its present erratic distribution (Stock, 1983; Cromley and McLafferty, 2002). In Nigeria, the lack of health insurance, ambulatory services and weak transport system further stresses the need for consideration of health services closeness to the population, especially in the remote

areas where car ownership is low (Okafor, 1991; Adedini *et al.*, 2014).

Access to healthcare in Low-and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs)

Globally, access to health care varies according to income distribution. Thus, the developed countries tend to have a better access to health care than the developing countries (Peters *et al.*, 2008). Similarly, healthcare distribution in the LMICs also follows the rich-poor lines leading to an inverse care (Hart, 1971). Therefore, health facilities are likely to cluster in the high-income neighbourhoods where car ownership is high and health need is low, but less in the low-income neighbourhoods who have opposite of those characteristics. Even when the population living in the low-income area is willing to risk the long-distance

travel to use the facilities in the high-income area, the chances of using the services may be reduced due to high-cost, low quality, inconsistent opening hours and poor staff-patients relationship (Peters *et al.*, 2008; Shah, 2011).

These problems originated from the budget deficit of 1980, which led to a cut in government expenditure on healthcare and a decline in the quantity and quality of services provided to the public (Lagarde and Palmer, 2011). Since government funds could no longer sustain strong health policies and sustainable healthcare planning; individuals since then began to make out-of-pocket payments for health services because there was no more free health care and health insurance. Even when services were purported to be free, illicit fees were charged for each patient's disposable medical instruments or they were to bring them from home.

Healthcare accessibility problems in the LMICs are summarised into; inverse care, impoverished care, fragmented care, unsafe care and misdirected care (Shah, 2011). According to Hart (1971), availability of healthcare tends to vary inversely with medical needs, especially where medical care is exposed to market forces. In the LMICs, urban areas with better resources and less medical needs have all mix of health services while the rural areas have less. Impoverished care is experienced in countries that have no universal healthcare insurance, thereby exposing the poor to high medical costs. Since the introduction of user-fees, access to health care in the LMICs has reduced significantly as a result of the inability to make out-of-pocket payment (Lagarde and Palmer, 2011).

Healthcare systems of many LMICs are fragmented; lacking information, resources, personnel, continuity and sustainability due to political instability and lack of concerted effort on the part of stakeholders in the health sector (Shah, 2011). Even in some countries where facilities and policies are in place, unsafe care accounts for deaths and disabilities as a result of wrong prescriptions, overdosage and hospital hygiene (Alsulami, Conroy and Choonara, 2013). Similarly, countries that have resources but without a good strategic health plan suffer misdirected care by spending more on curative care rather than basic healthcare (Shah, 2011). Primary health care facilities in many LMICs lack staff, facilities and decent quality. As a result, patients make self-referrals to hospitals and specialist hospitals which serve as the last resort of the health system.

Because of these challenges, the developing countries continue to fall under to burden of diseases morbidity, infant mortality, maternal mortality and epidemic outbreaks like Ebola. For instance, about 800 women die daily of childbirth-related issues globally; of which 99% are from developing countries and most of such deaths are preventable through prompt access to low-cost health care (World Health Organisation, 2017).

Access to healthcare in Nigeria

Nigeria's position as the most populous nation and strongest economy in Africa is a paradox of its health system; which is 187th out of 191 World Health Organisation (WHO) countries (World Health Organisation, 2000). With a population of 185 million as of 2016, extreme poverty, poor environmental quality, insurgency and insecurity; the budget for health care is bound to suffer significantly. Therefore, healthcare policies in the country are tailored to suit the limited funds. Even when funds are released, corruption and government bureaucracies perforate the effectiveness of the target intervention. Consequently, the Nigeria Health system has not experienced a significant improvement in the last two decades (Adeboye, 2014).

Nigeria is among the greatest burden bearers of diseases morbidity and mortalities in the world. Malaria, Tuberculosis (TB), Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) and malnutrition which have disappeared or reduced in many countries are still among the active sources of death in the country. Despite the successes achieved in the last decade in many countries, malaria remains a major public health problem in Nigeria with the greatest toll on under-five children and pregnant women (Malaria Elimination Programme, 2015). According to the Nigeria Malaria Indicator Survey of 2015 (Malaria Elimination Programme, 2015), malaria accounts for 60% of outpatient visits and 30% of admissions in the hospitals. It causes up to 11% of maternal mortalities, 25% of infant mortalities and 30% of under-five mortalities. It also records 110 million clinically diagnosed cases and estimated 300,000 malaria-related childhood deaths yearly.

Nigeria is also counted among the 14 high burden countries for TB and HIV, seventh among 30 high TB countries worldwide and second in Africa. According to Kanabus (2018), about 407,000 people in Nigeria get TB every year. The problem is further compounded with the presence of HIV. It is estimated that 63,000

HIV positive cases get TB each year and an estimated 115,00 HIV negative people die from TB (Kanabus, 2018). Beyond Malaria, TB and HIV; child malnutrition stunts 6 million children and more than half of them severely (UNICEF, 2015). Comparatively, Nigeria’s malnutrition rates are higher than those of West Africa and World malnutrition rates. While stunting, underweight and wasting are 37%, 29% and 18% respectively in Nigeria; they are 36%, 23% and 11% in West Africa; and 25%, 15% and 8% in the world (UNICEF, 2015).

Furthermore, Nigeria’s under-five mortality rate per 1000 live births is 104 and the third highest in the world (UNICEF, 2018). Life expectancy (m/f) is 55/56 and the probability of dying between 15 and 60 years (m/f) is 372/333 per 1000 (World Health Organisation, 2018). These are clear indications of poor access to health care in Nigeria and the situation is worsening considering the low expenditure on health (Table 1.1) which has not improved over the years.

Table 1.1: Nigeria Health Profile 2018

Total population (2016) (million)	185
Gross national income per capita (PPP international \$, 2013)	5
Life expectancy at birth m/f (years, 2016)	55/56
Probability of dying between 15 and 60 years m/f (per 1 000 population, 2016)	372/333
Total expenditure on health per capita (Intl \$, 2014)	217
Total expenditure on health as % of GDP (2014)	3.7

Source: World Health Organisation (2018)

The Nigerian healthcare system

A health system is the network of organisations, institutions and resources that deliver health services to the public. In Nigeria, two forms of health care services are recognised; modern and traditional healthcare (NPC, 2008). The modern health service includes all forms of organised healthcare that originated from Europe and colonial era, and the traditional healthcare is delivered by herbalists and spiritualists. The three key players in the Nigerian modern healthcare system are; government (public), private sector and charity (Amaghionyeodiwe, 2008). The public health care

system has a three-tier structure (i.e. primary, secondary and tertiary) which was fashioned after the three arms of government (i.e. federal, state and local government). The entry point of the health system is the primary health care (Amaghionyeodiwe, 2008), which is managed by the local council, though sometimes supported by the state, federal and charity organisations (NPC, 2008). Most primary health centres deliver only preventive and curative care to out-patients.

Secondary care is provided in General Hospitals which are situated in most local government administrative headquarters and managed by the state governments. General hospitals deliver inpatient and out-patient services, supervises and provide referral services for primary health centres. Tertiary cares are delivered by the teaching and specialist hospitals, which are mostly managed by the federal government. The teaching and specialist hospitals provide highly specialised services for orthopaedic, psychiatric, ophthalmic and infectious diseases. Although this structure is laid out, there are overlaps of functions due to fuzzy health policies, facility bypass and self-referrals by patients (Figure 1.1). The relationships among these three levels of care are shown in Figure 1.1.

The estimated number of all health facilities in the country in 2005 was 23,640; of which primary health facilities were 85.8%, secondary care were 14% and tertiary care were 0.2 % (Amaghionyeodiwe, 2008). There are 22 Federal medical centres, 20 Federal Teaching Hospitals and 13 Federal Specialty hospitals in the country (FMoH, 2014).

The private sector also makes significant contributions to the Nigeria health system and its impact increases yearly. It provides 60% of health care in the country also owns 38% of the facilities (Amaghionyeodiwe, 2008). The number of private health facilities doubled between 1987 (1,905) and 2000 (3,987) (Amaghionyeodiwe, 2008). Charity health facilities are few. In most cases, international and local charities provide support to existing public healthcare facilities. Traditional medicine in the country stays uncoordinated and there is little evidence about them. The influence of traditional health care practice tends to be stronger in the suburban and rural areas where geographical access to modern healthcare is limited.

Government policies on health care

As a way of tackling the complex health challenges and revamping the health system, the government of Nigeria planned and implemented a lot of health

policies. One of them is the Primary Health Care (PHC) which was launched in 1987 to improve healthcare throughout the country (Federal Ministry of Health, 2004). It was supposed to improve healthcare practices; promote health data collection and management; accelerate drug distribution; implement immunization programmes; increase health education and improve family planning. The PHC in the country failed due to lack of comprehensive national health policy (Federal Ministry of Health, 2004). As a result, Nigeria’s first comprehensive national health policy was promulgated in 1988. It was supposed to address access to health care; improve health indicators; ensure efficient immunization administration; increase funding and improve health information systems. When the policy did not address those issues, it was revised in 2004 to correct the weaknesses while incorporating modern features in standard health systems in the world. The salient features of the new policy were; collaborating with the New Partnership for African Development (NEPAD), the actualization of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and development of a comprehensive health reform that incorporates New Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS).

Health Development Plan Framework (NSHDP 2009 – 2015) (Federal Ministry of Health, 2009). The main aim of NSHDP (2009 – 2015) was to make significant improvements in the health status of Nigerians, through developing and strengthening efficient health care system.

The Nigerian government has made a considerable number of policies in the last three decades with the aim to improve the weak healthcare system in the country. However, most of them lacked measurable goals and sustainability. Some of the policies and interventions were inspired by politics, some were tailored to the budget size and most of them lacked geographical accessibility. Therefore, successfully implemented interventions faced low utilisation or clustered in locations with similar services; and the health system experienced insignificant or no improvement in the end.

Financing healthcare in Nigeria

Nigeria’s financial commitment to health care is one of the least in the world despite its strong economic position in Africa and population size. The country’s budget for health has not improved in the last 43 years but declining. The total budget for health was about 6

Figure 1.1: Nigerian healthcare system; relationship and referral pattern

per cent of the national budget in the 1970s (Ayeni, Rushton and McNulty, 1987). In the year 2000, it was 0.8 per cent

The overall objective was to strengthen the national health care system and provide affordable, quality, equitable and accessible health care to the population while achieving the MDGs. In July 2009, the national health policy was upgraded to the National Strategic

(Ogunbodede, 2004) and in 2008 it was increased to 4 per cent (Burke and Sridhar, 2013). In 2013 and 2014, it was only 6.1 per cent and 6 per cent of the country’s GDP respectively (Ihekweazu, 2014), while the per

capita budget for health was \$161 in 2013 (World Health Organisation, 2014). In the year 2010, the government's overall spending on health dropped to 3.5 per cent, and 5.9% of total expenditure on health that year came from external funds. Presently, the total budget for health care is only 3.7% of the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (World Health Organisation, 2018).

The health sector in Nigeria enjoys multilateral and bilateral supports (Burke and Sridhar, 2013). However, the largest contribution to national expenditures on health is from private sources' out-of-pocket payments for health services (Federal Ministry of Health, 2004). The government had no strategically planned health care funding modalities and is presently unable to afford universal health insurance for all citizens. Therefore, an insurance scheme was introduced to reduce the burden of health care financing on the government and individuals.

National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS)

The NHIS was implemented in 2005 (National Health Insurance Scheme, 2015). The scheme was formed under the Public Private Partnership (PPP). It is a form of health insurance that is managed like the United States Health Management Organisation (HMOs). The scheme was initially established in 1999 with the aim of making health care available for all Nigerians at an affordable cost through a prepayment system. The long-term goal of the scheme is to provide universal health care coverage for the population. The various segments are Formal Sector Social Health Insurance (FSSHI); Urban Self-employed Social Health Insurance (USSHI); Rural Community Social Health Insurance (RCSHI); Children Under-five Social Health Insurance (CUSHI); Permanently Disabled Persons Social Health Insurance (PDPSHI); Prison Inmates Social Health Insurance (PISHI); Tertiary Institutions and Voluntary Participants Social Health Insurance (TIVPSHI); and Armed Forces, Police and other Uniformed Services Scheme (AFPUSS).

The target was to increase NHIS participation to 30% by 2015 (National Health Insurance Scheme, 2015). However, national participation in the NHIS after 13 years was only 3 per cent in mid-2012 which is significantly lower than other developing countries such as Colombia (95%) and India (19%) (Dutta *et al.*, 2013). The success of the NHIS is impeded by its poor accessibility because accredited facilities are clustered in urban areas which are estimated to have more market potentials.

Access to health care services

Health care is "the prevention, treatment, and management of illness and the preservation of mental and physical well-being through the services offered by the medical and allied health professionals" (Farlex, 2018). It is a structured delivery of medical services to individuals or communities. Health care is a basic necessity; thus, Gulliford *et al.* (2002) named it "a social commodity" and "human right". However, the extent an individual can exercise such a right is limited, especially in developing countries that have no universal health insurance. Penchansky and Thomas (1981), defined access as a fit between the population and healthcare supplier. According to MacKinney *et al.* (2014), access is an interplay of definitions, measures, barriers and framework. Access to health services implies adequacy and timely reach of health services when needed in order to maintain a healthy living (Gulliford *et al.*, 2002). Thus, the proximity of health services to the population irrespective personal circumstances may improve their physical and mental wellbeing.

However, Whitehead *et al.* (1997), argued that proximity to healthcare alone is insufficient in the concept of accessibility. They argued that the amount of information the individual has affects the level of access to the services. Therefore, access comprises variety, quality, convenience, cost and information about the needed service. Rogers, Flowers and Pencheon (1999) in support of Whitehead *et al.* (1997), argued that the study of access to any service requires a framework of systems approach which enables decision makers to make timely services available in the right locations. In the systems approach, access is a part of a system (urban or rural) that depends on other components to succeed. For instance, the health service may be available within reach, but not at the quantity or quality demanded. Thus, access involves availability, utilisation, relevance, effectiveness and equity (Chapman *et al.*, 2004).

Access to health services differs depending on the level of care sought after. Studies have established that primary health services are more accessible than secondary and specialist health services (Feikin *et al.*, 2009; Al-Taiar *et al.*, 2010). In summary, access is a network of physical, social and financial links between the population and health service providers. In planning, access decides 'who is served already', 'who is to be served now' and 'who is to be served later'; considering available resources.

Concepts of access

Traditionally, access is often linked to territory and boundary; hence, in the legal parlance, there is ‘right of way’ and ‘right to use’. In the modern context, access includes social, political, economic and technological aspects of the health system (Semm and Palang, 2010). The advancement in information technology, telecommunication and the internet has brought a shift to the perception of access to health care. Currently, the need to travel is gradually reducing as telemedicine advances in many countries. Therefore, the focus of access is set to shift towards availability of connectible technologies. However, such advancements will be more applicable to primary care in the technologically advanced countries.

Access can be integral or relative (Ingram, 1971). Relative access is the degree of interconnection between two points, while integral access measures the degree of interconnection among points on the same surface. In the integral approach, several alternatives must be forgone for a single provider. For instance, a patient must choose from the doctor, pharmacist, drug store or traditional healthcare service for an episode of sickness. The main challenge of integral access measurement is data availability.

Relative access is usually measured in relation to the system in which the user and supplier of the service exist. The relationship between the two locations can be explained in the concept of access in a ‘free system’ (Hennessy, Merro and Rathke, 2004). The concept is derived from the systems theory with the assumption that an individual in the system has no restriction to the resources that are available within the system. Access in this case is the condition in space which allows an object in a free system at an established location A to reach a destination B. The two locations are often separated in space by social values, distance, time and/or cost. The overall mobility depends on the resources available and the distance to alternative locations (Hennessy, Merro and Rathke, 2004). In the determination of access to health care, it is assumed that a patient has no restriction on the transport system, cost and social barriers.

Dimensions of access

The five dimensions of access by Penchansky and Thomas (1981) are; availability, accessibility, accommodation, affordability and acceptability of the service. They are combinations of an individual’s needs and the factors that must be fulfilled before it is

satisfied. The five dimensions of access by Penchansky and Thomas (1981), were later modified by Peters *et al.* (2008) into four groups, namely; geographical accessibility, availability, financial accessibility and acceptability.

Availability

In healthcare delivery, availability shows the number of health resources that are ready to be used by patients; for instance, the number of specialist services, physicians, and healthcare facilities (Penchansky and Thomas, 1981). This dimension of access is within the control of the government, planners and decision makers in the health sector who ensure the availability of health facilities, general practice doctors, surgeons, nurses, dentist and medical laboratory scientists. Effective planning for equitable health service delivery requires the knowledge of facility to patient ratio, physician to population ratio, nurses to population ratio, midwives to female population ratio. Sometimes it might be important to know the ratio of essential health facility equipment to a target population. For instance, planners need to know the ratio of women to facilities offering emergency obstetric and neonatal services. In locations that are prone to an outbreak of a disease like diarrhoea; the ratio of diarrhoea facilities to the population is very vital in the plan for future outbreaks. Since some health services do not operate throughout the day, availability goes beyond the density of facilities and health personnel to include opening time, waiting times and material (Peters *et al.*, 2008).

Accommodation

Accommodation is close to availability (Peters *et al.*, 2008), though it highlights the effect of satisfaction with aspects of the service like appointment system, opening hours, waiting times and flexible services (Penchansky and Thomas, 1981). It is concerned with what happens when a potential user becomes an actual user. In developed countries, automated appointment systems are used to reduce waiting times and improve flexibility while in the LMICs, hospital appointment systems are mostly on papers. Therefore, waiting times may be unbearably long because of the physician-patient ratio, poor appointment or weak referral systems. The first impression of satisfaction may decide the chances of using the same facility in the future.

Affordability

Access to health care also depends on the cost, ability to pay and payment methods. Affordability (Penchansky and Thomas, 1981) or financial accessibility (Peters *et al.*, 2008) is related to the ability

or willingness to pay, health insurance, credit facility and price of the service. The forces of demand and supply control this dimension of access. Access and utilisation of health services tend to be higher in countries that have adopted universal access to health care or have a form of health insurance (Lagarde and Palmer, 2011). Besides the cost of treatment, the overall healthcare cost is bound to increase if the health facility is far from home.

Acceptability

Acceptability comprises the client's perception of quality, social status, faith and other attributes of the health service (Penchansky and Thomas, 1981). Although, the declaration of Alma-Ata emphasised the provision of primary health services that are culturally acceptable, very little about this is found in the literature (Peters *et al.*, 2008). The satisfaction of quality (Andaleeb, 2001), gender inequality (Standing, 1997), the attitude of health professionals (Brugha and Zwi, 1998), social status and cultural norms can increase or reduce the utilisation of the health services significantly. Lack of acceptability is one of the leading causes of health facilities bypass and low utilisation of government-managed health facilities in developing countries (Akin and Hutchinson, 1999).

Geographic accessibility

Accessibility otherwise called geographical access (Peters *et al.*, 2008) is the physical link between the potential user and the facility; considering travel time, distance and cost (Penchansky and Thomas, 1981). It is concerned with accessibility and availability of health services (Guagliardo, 2004). This dimension of access is a function of good road networks and transport systems. It varies depending on the location of residence and the number of facilities; therefore, some locations are more accessible than others. For instance, the distribution of health services tend to favour urban areas with high population density more than the rural dwellers; hence, deprivation (Peters *et al.*, 2008).

Apart from the bad road network, geographical access can be limited by environmental features like climate change, rivers, valleys and mountains. In low-lying locations, access tends to reduce in the wet seasons because of flooding (Blanford *et al.*, 2012). Some developed countries in the last decade have reduced the barriers of physical access by use of safety helicopters and drones in times of emergency. With the advancement of mobile telecommunication and information technology, some countries have also used telemedicine to connect patients via smartphones and

the internet to medical services. In the developing countries where these technologies are unavailable or unreliable, the solution is to increase geographical accessibility of health facilities.

Prioritising geographical access to healthcare in Nigeria

The focus of planners and researchers over the years have been on financing healthcare and increasing human resources, without that realisation that making geographical access a priority would have solved both problems. Every year, a substantial portion of Nigeria's meagre budget on healthcare is lost to healthcare interventions that were incomplete, never used or lying redundant. New health facilities fold up or remain underutilised shortly after commissioning because location accessibility was not considered at the planning stage. A typical example is the NHIS, in which some people who subscribed to the service are unable to use it because of distance; since the majority of the facilities are crowded in urban areas.

Considering the limited resources in the country, incorporating geographical access to healthcare planning can reduce the number of facilities to be sited while serving a larger population at a shorter distance. The solution is in the use of Location-Allocation Models (LAMs). LAMs allow planners to site health facilities at optimised locations using simple parameters about the users and the proposed facilities (Oppong, 1996; Rahman and Smith, 2000). Many countries have successfully used LAMs to increase population access while reducing the budget for healthcare. A typical example was the reallocation of dialysis centres in the United States of America which saved the state \$5 million (Pliskin and Tell, 1981). Locating fewer health facilities at optimal locations will leave a substantial amount which can be plunged back into the health system to improve the quality of the service and human resources.

The distribution of health facilities in Nigeria has always been the prerogative of the top manager of the health system (e.g. Minister of Health) who is usually a politician (Ayeni, Rushton and McNulty, 1987). Therefore, new health facilities locations are sometimes selected based on party commitment or used as a reward to faithful voters. Setting aside political sentiments and embracing location viability of healthcare interventions will enable health planners to target locations with genuine health needs instead of political interests.

Distance to healthcare is a major determinant of prompt utilisation of effective treatment (Makita-Ikouaya *et al.*, 2010; Yao *et al.*, 2012; Sabde, De Costa and Diwan, 2014). The delay in the use of healthcare can lead to disease severity, hospitalisation or death. Also, long distance to the health facility could lead to incomplete antenatal care, pregnancy complications, maternal mortality and neonatal death (Ronsmans, Graham and Group, 2006). Reducing maternal and under-five mortalities in Nigeria requires a conscientious effort to bring healthcare closer to the population; especially in the rural areas where the outcomes are higher.

Apart from saving lives and the budget; prioritising geographical access in healthcare planning will reduce the cost of care, road travel, the risk of accident and save the environment. The overall cost of treatment is expected to increase as the distance to health facility increases. Therefore, the proximity of facilities will encourage the population to seek health care promptly (Kurihara and Kato, 2007), and they will have extra money to save. When the need to travel is reduced, less fuel will be used, and environmental pollution will be reduced (Santos, Behrendt and Teytelboym, 2010). Apart from environmental pollution, excessive travels to health facilities on Nigeria's bad roads may increase the risk of accident (Ekanem, Aboh and Okolisah, 2017), disease severity and complication.

Conclusion

Geographical access is a vital component of the health system. Although this paper does not undermine the importance of finance, quality and human resources, it stresses that they are magnified by the lack of inclusion of location accessibility at the planning stage. After the implementation, it becomes difficult to adjust the locations of facilities without having to make a huge financial sacrifice. Since the recession is still looming and the health system is failing, it is high time we used a few locations of health facilities to achieve more.

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